

Search Strategy

A comprehensive literature search was conducted in Web of Science, Scopus (Elsevier), PubMed and APA PsycInfo. The search was conducted using English keywords and Boolean operators specific to each database. The process adheres to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines to ensure methodological transparency and reproducibility of the results (Page et al., 2021).

Following keywords were used in the search:

((gamb* OR betting OR bets OR wager) AND ("risk factor*" OR determinant* OR "contributing factor*" OR predictor* OR caus* OR vulnerabilit* OR outcome* OR risk* OR exposur*) AND (adolescen* OR "young adult*" OR "young people" OR "young person" OR "emerging adult*" OR youth))